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ABSTRACTS

KEYNOTE LECTURES, COMMUNICATIONS, POSTERS

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Link to posters

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3.1 = Carpological analysis of a Roman well at the site of *Alba Fucens* (Abruzzi, Italy)

Claudia Moricca¹, Gilda Russo², Emanuela Ceccaroni³, Gabriele Favero¹, Laura Sadori¹

¹Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome, Piazzale Aldo Moro 5, 00185 Roma, Italy;

²Istituto di Scienze del Patrimonio Culturale, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Strada della Neve s.n.c., Via Salaria km 29.300, 00010 Montelibretti, Italy; ³Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio per le Province di Chieti e Pescara, Via degli Agostiniani 14, 66100 Chieti, Italy

Abruzzo is, after Valle d'Aosta, the second least investigated Italian Region in terms of archaeobotanical analyses, with only four sites published so far (1, 2). Of these, only one is of Roman age (3).

In this perspective, the archaeological site of *Alba Fucens* (L'Aquila) represents a great addition to the state of the art. Presumably founded by the Equi, an Italic tribe, *Alba Fucens* (Fig. 1) became an important Roman colony at the end of the 4th century BC. Inscriptions testify its prosperity during the Imperial period. Its splendor ceased in 537 A.D. during the Gothic war.

The archaeological materials, deriving from years of excavation campaigns led by the “Soprintendenza per i Beni Archeologici dell'Abruzzo”, are until now poorly investigated from a scientific perspective. The present study focuses on plant remains recovered from a Roman well. Located in the square of the Sanctuary of Hercules, the well was identified during the excavations of 2011. It is possible to suppose that the filling of the well is the result of an action after the destruction of the sanctuary of Hercules following an earthquake in the Late Roman period. Part of the collapsed materials was moved into the reservoir, to recover practicable space in the square of the sanctuary, located along the Via Valeria in a lowered and protected position.

The archaeobotanical analysis was performed on six soil samples (total of 12.6 kg), collected from six different Stratigraphic Units (SUs) from the filling of the well. The progressive numbering of the SUs indicates a greater depth with respect to the planking level. Separation of plant macro-remains was performed by wet sieving at the *Museo delle Paludi* in Celano (Soprintendenza Archeologia, Belle Arti e Paesaggio per le Province di Chieti e Pescara).

More than 1500 carpological remains preserved by waterlogging were identified in the studied sediment. These are represented by 70 different taxa, belonging to vascular plants and mosses. Carpological remains are mostly attributable to gathered fruit plants (e.g. *Corylus avellana* L., *Juglans regia* L. and *Sambucus nigra* L.) and spontaneous herbaceous species (e.g. *Marrubium vulgare* L. and *Polygonum rurivagum* Jord. ex Boreau).

Overall, the assemblage describes Apennine grasslands, influenced by human presence. The study also provides precious information about the diet of the Roman inhabitants of the site and the exploitation of the natural resources that the surrounding environment had to offer.

Fig. 1. The archaeological site of *Alba Fucens*.

1) M. Mariotti Lippi, A. Florenzano, R. Rinaldi et al. (2018) *Flora Mediterranea*, 28, 365-376.

2) A.M. Mercuri, E. Allevato, D. Arobba et al. (2015) *Rev. Paleobot. Palynol.*, 218, 250-266.

3) C. Shelton (2009) *Food, economy and identity in the Sangro River Valley, Abruzzo, Italy, 650 B.C. – A.D. 150*. Boston University, PhD dissertation.